

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D2.3

Manual for Citizen Science community building

SDA Bocconi

March, 2022

The INCENTIVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101005330

PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	INCENTIVE – Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society.
START DATE	1 February 2021
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	www.incentive-project.eu
COORDINATOR	Universiteit Twente (DesignLab) (NL)
PROJECT OVERVIEW	INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

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Grant Agreement: 101005330 | Coordination and Support Action | 2021 – 2023 | Duration: 36 months

Topic: Swafs-23-2020 - Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science

D2.3: Manual for Citizen Science community building

Issued by:	SDA Bocconi
Issue date:	31/03/2022
Due date:	31/03/2022
Work Package Leader:	UT

Start date of project: 1 February 2021

Duration: 36 months

DOCUMENT HISTORY		
Version	Date	Changes
v0.1	17/03/2022	Initial version prepared by SDA
v0.2	21/03/2022	Quality Review by CM (ECSA) and MVDB (UT)
v0.3	28/03/2022	Revised version of the deliverable
v0.9	30/03/2022	Revised version of the deliverable after final check by PC (UT)
v1.0	31/03/2022	Final version submitted to the portal

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	X
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Table of Contents

Executive summary	9
1. Introduction	10
2. Background	11
2.1 Determinants behind stakeholders' engagement.....	11
2.1.1 <i>Determinants of co-production</i>	<i>11</i>
2.2 Quadruple Helix stakeholders' interests toward Citizen Science	13
2.2.1 <i>Main factors emerging from the literature</i>	<i>13</i>
2.2.2 <i>Main factors emerging from deliverables' results.....</i>	<i>15</i>
2.3 Identification and selection of the engagement tools	16
2.3.1 <i>Main factors emerging from deliverables' results.....</i>	<i>16</i>
2.3.2 <i>Identification of the most appropriate testable tools.....</i>	<i>20</i>
3. Research design.....	22
4. Findings.....	23
4.1 Greece	29
4.2 Lithuania.....	30
4.3 The Netherlands.....	31
4.4 Spain	32
4.5 Focus on specific categories	33
4.5.1 <i>Women.....</i>	<i>34</i>
4.5.2 <i>Seniors</i>	<i>36</i>
4.5.3 <i>Participants with low levels of education</i>	<i>39</i>
5. Discussion	42
6. Guidelines to incentivise and engage Quadruple Helix stakeholders in Citizen Science Hubs	44
6.1 What is citizen engagement in CSH?.....	44
6.2 Under which conditions does citizen engagement enhance CSH activities?.....	45
6.3 How to use the incentivisation tools	46
6.3.1 <i>Mode of involvement</i>	<i>46</i>
6.3.2 <i>Expert facilitator.....</i>	<i>48</i>

6.3.3	<i>Invest in continuous training for stakeholders</i>	49
6.3.4	<i>Monetary and non-monetary Incentives</i>	51
6.3.5	<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	53
6.3.6	<i>Motivation</i>	55
6.4	How to develop a stakeholder engagement plan.....	56
6.4.1	<i>Addressing potential barriers</i>	57
7.	Implications and future work for the INCENTIVE project	59
8.	References	61
9.	Appendix	66

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Relevance of the six tools - Greece.....	26
Figure 2:	Relevance of the six tools - Lithuania	26
Figure 3:	Relevance of the six tools - the Netherlands.....	26
Figure 4:	Relevance of the six tools - Spain	27
Figure 5:	Preference shares for each level of the six tools – Greece.....	30
Figure 6:	Preference shares for each level of the six tools – Lithuania	31
Figure 7:	Preference shares for each level of the six tools – the Netherlands.....	32
Figure 8:	Preference shares for each level of the six tools – Spain.....	33
Figure 9:	Relevance of the six tools in Greece – Women	34
Figure 10:	Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania – Women	34
Figure 11:	Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands – Women.....	35
Figure 12:	Relevance of the six tools in Spain – Women	36
Figure 13:	Relevance of the six tools in Greece – Seniors	37
Figure 14:	Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania – Seniors	37
Figure 15:	Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands – Seniors	38
Figure 16:	Relevance of the six tools in Spain – Seniors	38
Figure 17:	Relevance of the six tools in Greece – People with low levels of education.....	39
Figure 18:	Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania – People with low levels of education	39
Figure 19:	Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands – People with low levels of education..	40

Figure 20: Relevance of the six tools in Spain – People with low levels of education41

List of Tables

Table 1: Most common tools.....	19
Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics.....	23
Table 3: CS-related questions per country	24
Table 4: Optimal tools to use for engagement in CSHs	28
Table 5: Country-specific tools of engagement.....	29

Abbreviations

RPFO(s)	Research Performing and Funding Organization(s)
CS	Citizen Science
CSH(s)	Citizen Science Hub(s)
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
SDA	SDA Bocconi
UAB	Universidad Autonoma de Barcelona
UT	Universiteit Twente
UZH	Universität Zurich
VG TU	Vilniaus Gedimino Technikos Universitetas
e.g.	Exempli gratia
i.e.	Id est
WP	Work Package
RQ	Research Question
QH	Quadruple Helix

Executive summary

The deliverable D2.3 “Manual for Citizen Science community building” has been developed under the framework of the H2020 INCENTIVE project. This project aims at empowering European Research Performing and Funding Organizations (RPFOS) to establish sustainable transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent Citizen Science (CS).

While the RPFOS are ultimately responsible for designing, setting up, and operating their CSHs, the consortium’s partners provided inspiration with a set of baseline elements for the governance, operating, and monitoring model of the hubs, and guidance with the core principle of RRI. This deliverable elaborates a manual and defines the tools needed to incentivise and engage QH stakeholders in the Citizen Science Hubs (CSHs) of the four RPFOS (University of Twente, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University). Also, this task builds on the work of other Work Packages (in particular D1.2 “Profile of the 4 RPFOS: Institutional structure, capacity and needs”, D1.3 “Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs”, and D2.1 “Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes”). To collect further information, an online survey has been developed, involving an overall sample of 1052 participants representative of the four countries (Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands and Spain). The results provide relevant insights for what concerns the most effective tools to be implemented in the four local contexts to foster stakeholders’ engagement and maintain it over time.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 introduces the aim of the manual, together with the research question and the methodological approach to tackle it.
- Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background, for what concerns the individual willingness to co-produce and participate in Citizen Science projects and the main tools exploited in the literature.
- Chapter 3 moves towards the empirical part of the manual, presenting the methodological approach exploited to test some of the most relevant tools chosen from the previous chapter.
- Chapter 4 presents the main evidence of a survey, with a focus on potential cultural heterogeneities and on specific potentially underrepresented categories of citizens.
- Chapter 5 concludes, by summarising the main results.
- Chapter 6 provides concrete guidelines to incentivise stakeholders, while Chapter 7 focuses on further implications.
- The Appendix presents the text of the survey plus some additional tables.

1. Introduction

In the framework of WP2, aimed at “Co-creating the Citizen Science Hubs”, the current deliverable focuses on the development of a manual aimed at supporting the local RPFs in the establishment of the CSHs. In particular, the deliverable D2.3 (“Manual for Citizen Science Community Building”) provides a theoretical and empirical overview of the most promising tools, in terms of their potential to attract and engage a heterogeneous crowd.

To achieve this scope, we implemented the following steps:

- Reviewed the previous deliverables (in particular D1.2 “Profile of the 4 RPFs: Institutional structure, capacity and needs”, D1.3 “Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs”, and D2.1 “Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes” to get insights about the main motivators pushing different QH stakeholders into the CS world in different cultural contexts;
- Analysed the relevant literature on engagement tools and their implementation with QH stakeholders and in CSHs;
- Developed a survey, in light of the evidence gathered from the previous sources, to test the relative importance of some of the main engagement tools;
- Implemented the survey with representative samples of the local RPFs’ populations and conducted a subsequent analysis of the tools’ effectiveness;
- Analysed the results for providing suggestions for the RPFs about the best strategies to engage stakeholders in CSHs.

For this purpose, the scope of this manual is to identify and test tools to stimulate stakeholders’ incentivisation in CSHs. Although there already exist projects (also within the Horizon 2020 framework) that focus on CS initiatives and offer recommendations for citizens’ engagement, the main novelty of this manual is that it builds on the existing literature on CS, QH stakeholders, and Public Service Logic to concretely test the importance of the most promising engagement tools in comparative and absolute terms. Through a conjoint analysis (a survey-based statistical technique to measure the influence of certain tools on individuals’ decisions), we identified the role of six tools, which are supposed to influence individuals’ willingness and/or ability to engage in co-creation activities like CSHs. These tools took into account the mode of involvement, the presence of an expert facilitator, the possibility to receive continuous training and learning opportunities, the role of monetary and non-monetary incentives, the ideal pool of participants, and the project focus on public value versus private interest topics.

The manual is structured as follows: Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background (based on the literature and the already available INCENTIVE deliverables) that characterises the QH stakeholders’ features. Chapter 3 discusses the methods used to address the RQ, while Chapter 4 provides the main evidence for relative and absolute importance of some of the most promising engagement tools. Chapter 5 summarises the main evidence. Finally, Chapter 6 provides concrete guidelines for the four local RPFs to incentivise and engage QH stakeholders, while Chapter 7 presents some implications and concludes.

2. Background

The first part of this chapter aims to focus on the already available information concerning the determinants behind the individual's willingness to participate in co-creation and co-production initiatives (like the CSHs). We took inspiration from the pieces of literature on co-production, QH stakeholders, and CS regarding the more theoretical insights, while the previous deliverables of INCENTIVE have been examined for what concerns the evidence on the concrete stakeholders' motivations. Then, we dedicated our attention to the engagement tools that have been proven, or are supposed, to influence such individual motivations, revising the main instruments retrieved from the aforementioned literature and identifying the most promising ones.

2.1 Determinants behind stakeholders' engagement

When looking at the definition of CS, one of the key aspects that emerges and characterises this kind of initiatives is the co-production component (Vohland et al. 2021, chapter 11). Depending on the CSH, citizens actively participate at different stages, collaborating with academics and the other actors involved in the "production" of science. Furthermore, CSHs can have different degrees of involvement, depending on whether they are *contributory*, *collaborative*, or *co-creative* projects (Bonney et al. 2009). In light of this, taking the literature on co-production as reference becomes fundamental to developing a centred theoretical framework, able to identify the main factors that drive or hinder stakeholders' willingness to participate and engage in CSHs.

When discussing co-production, several different definitions of this concept can be retrieved from the literature. The main one is provided by Ostrom (1996, 1073), who defines co-production as "the process through which inputs used to produce a service are contributed by individuals who are not in the same organisation". Brudney and England (1983) describe the phenomenon in more general terms as citizens' involvement in the service delivery process. Other contributions highlight the active role of all the involved subjects in terms of resources contribution, such as time, knowledge, and expertise (Bovaird 2007; Voorberg et al. 2018); this enhances the quantity and quality of delivered public services (Andersen et al. 2017; Brudney 1983; Jakobsen and Andersen 2013; Pestoff 2006).

2.1.1 Determinants of co-production

Overall, research on co-production emphasises two factors as particularly important (Alford 2002; Jakobsen 2013; Porter 2012): ability and motivation. Initiatives targeted at fostering both these factors are a means for local governments to increase citizen co-production (Alford 2002; Brudney 1983; Jakobsen 2013; Percy 1984).

The first type of initiative incorporates the theoretical assumption that increasing citizens' ability to co-produce may enhance their participation in the co-production of public services (Alford 2002; Brudney 1983; Percy 1984). The argument is based on the logic that lifting the constraints

on citizens' ability to co-produce by providing resources in the form of knowledge and materials necessary may enhance their level of co-production (Jakobsen 2013; Jakobsen and Andersen 2013).

The second type of initiative draws on some of the same theoretical assumptions, namely that informing citizens about the benefits of co-production will encourage them to co-produce (Brudney 1983; Rosentraub and Sharp 1981). Citizens who do not know how to co-produce are less likely to participate, and an initiative that informs citizens via booklets or leaflets will improve their ability and motivation (Thomsen and Jakobsen 2015). Moreover, sharing knowledge about co-production and CS and how citizens' input matters may encourage them to co-produce.

Increasing ability to co-produce

Concerning citizens' ability, two categories of interventions are typically recognised as facilitators (Alford 2002):

- Those that make the co-production task easier;
- Those that enhance the citizen's own capacities to co-produce.

With regard to the first category, Alford (2009, 50) highlights how "the use of technology seems to have been an important factor in simplifying the complexity of the co-productive work. Indeed, the development and application of technology, especially in information systems and communications, seem to offer great potential for facilitating client co-production."

Among the instruments belonging to the second category, providing information, advice, or training are typical examples, which have a relevant role both at the point of access (Alford 2002; Jakobsen 2013) and during the process of interaction (Prahalad and Ramaswamy 2004). These types of tools may be advantageous for those who lack prior knowledge necessary to contribute to and benefit from the co-production process (Jakobsen and Andersen 2013). At the same time, how such information is presented is also fundamental to stimulating participation (Porumbescu et al. 2017).

Increasing willingness to co-produce

Alford (2002, 2009) classifies motivators into five voices:

- Sanctions. They usually are ineffective (or even counterproductive) in stimulating positive behaviours like co-producing as they convey the wrong message that this type of involvement is unpleasant and therefore to be avoided. Sanctions might increase compliance, but not willingness and overall engagement. Nevertheless, they "elicit co-production by facilitating the mobilisation of other types of incentives" (Alford 2002, 43).
- Material rewards. They typically relate to benefits like monetary rewards, goods, or services. As for sanctions, material rewards also have to be calibrated if implemented. In fact, drawing on the concepts of social and economic exchange (Blau 1964), the risk of

committing participation to an economic exchange is that the effort put by citizens will then be limited to what is economically agreed. “If they are willing to contribute time and effort to organisational purposes, they do so for their own good reasons, which are much more complex than money or the avoidance of punishment” (Alford 2002, 45). This is particularly true for more complex co-productive tasks, where non-material rewards seem more effective, while material rewards shall be associated with simpler tasks (Alford 2009). Furthermore, the literature on public administration shows that the effects of monetary rewards are marginal (Perry et al. 2009; Voorberg et al. 2018).

- Intrinsic rewards. They are organisational actions or behaviours that enhance the sense of satisfaction from feeling competent and autonomous or from the enjoyment of an activity. Intrinsic rewards differ from solidary incentives or normative appeals (see below) in that they resonate with individual fulfilment.
- Solidary incentives. They can be defined as “the rewards of associating with others, such as socialising, the sense of group membership and identification, being well regarded, and fun and conviviality” (Alford 2002, 35; Clark and Wilson 1961).
- Normative appeals. They are explicit communications from the organisation, or implicit meanings conveyed by organisational actions or behaviours, which signal identification with or support for valued social and moral ideals or principles.

The effectiveness of each of these motivations depends on the form of co-production being promoted (Alford 2002). Individualistic initiatives are prompted more by material incentives, while collective ones are encouraged mostly by solidary incentives.

2.2 Quadruple Helix stakeholders’ interests toward Citizen Science

After identifying the overall framework that presents the categorisation of the main drivers behind the individual decision to participate in co-production activities, this Section focuses on the relevant knowledge that emerged from the overall literature and the already published INCENTIVE deliverables. In this way, we can utilise useful insights arising from the four local contexts to better tailor the engagement tools to be identified and tested.

In Section 2.2.1, we summarise some theoretical insights that can be of relevance to this Deliverable 2.3. Successively, we focus on the evidence from the INCENTIVE sources, presenting those factors that are already shown to be relevant to the individual’s motivation and ability to join CSHs.

2.2.1 Main factors emerging from the literature

To integrate the theoretical framework, useful insights can be retrieved from the already available INCENTIVE deliverables, particularly from D1.3 “Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs” and its Section

4.3.2 “Status, trends and enabling/hindering factors on citizen science at the RPFOS ecosystem”. On this basis, complementary information can be retrieved from other external sources. The reason behind using this approach is to maintain a fil rouge across deliverables, exploiting a common theoretical framework when applicable.

Starting from the drivers and enabling factors, in D1.3 “Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs” they have been categorised into those that relate to individual motivations (subjective perceptions, desires and personal goals) and those that derive from objective circumstances of the macro-environment (cultural, social and economic conditions). Clearly, CSHs have a limited impact on the latter category, so we focus our attention on the former one. Emotional and psychosocial motivations include personal interest, curiosity and enthusiasm for the scientific project, as well as self-prestige and personal growth associated with fostering personal reputation and acquiring new skills (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Jennett et al. 2016; Kragh 2016; Larson et al. 2020; Rotman et al. 2014a). Moreover, the sense of fulfilment from feeling like an active member of the society and feeling useful to the scientific community plays a role (Jennett et al. 2016; Kragh 2016; Rotman et al. 2014b; Scotland Counts 2016). Many of these factors can also be retrieved from Vohland et al. (2021; see Chapter 13), for instance, when considering the coherence between personal interests and the aim of the CSH (Roman et al. 2020), or the social interaction stimulus that stems from interacting with scientists (Havens et al. 2012) and becoming part of a community of like-minded people (Asah and Blahna 2012). Other non-emotional drivers are linked to the possibility of obtaining concrete benefits, like improving the CV and career track (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Larson et al. 2020), monetary compensations for the efforts and time devoted or non-monetary incentives such as certificates (Asingizwe et al. 2020). Other aspects that are worth mentioning are the alignment between participants’ local needs and interests with scientific priorities (Pocock et al. 2018), the possibility to enjoy training courses in close interaction with scientists (Rotman et al. 2014a), and gamification elements (Vohland et al. 2021). Further, particularly relevant factors relate to public recognition and acknowledgement for the efforts made (Garcia-Soto et al. 2017; Jennett et al. 2016; Rotman et al. 2014a; Rotman et al. 2014b), together with the ability to convey clear instructions and develop effective feedback channels (Mitchell et al. 2017; Rotman et al. 2014a). Accountability and transparency concerning data management are fundamental as well to generate trust and maintain engagement (Rotman et al. 2014a,b).

Looking at those factors that constitute a barrier, there exists a range of elements that negatively affects individuals’ participation and that corresponds to the absence or negative framing of the aforementioned enabling factors (e.g., lack of transparency, lack of trust, poor communication, poor training) (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Hecker et al. 2018; Nguyen and Marques 2021; Pocock et al. 2018; Rotman et al. 2014b). Besides them, peculiar elements of the demotivating factors include the false perception of being unable to contribute to the CSH in terms of quantity and quality standards (Garcia-Soto et al. 2017; Martin et al. 2016; Mitchell et al. 2017; Pocock et al. 2018), general inertia (Pocock et al. 2018), concerns about data and privacy management (Hecker et al. 2018), excessively centralised project structures (August et al. 2019; Rotman et al. 2014b), and time constraints (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Collins et al. 2015; Kleinke et al. 2018; Martin et al. 2016; Rotman et al. 2014b).

One aspect deserving attention that applies to all the aforementioned factors is that they can change over time and at different stages of stakeholders' participation (Crowston and Fagnot 2008; Eveleigh et al. 2014; Land-Zandstra et al. 2016; Rotman et al. 2012; Vohland et al. 2021).

2.2.2 Main factors emerging from deliverables' results

After the revision of the main evidence retrieved from the literature, this paragraph focuses on what has already been identified in the previously released INCENTIVE deliverables to integrate and systematise the previous insights and gather established evidence. The information on the main motivating and hindering factors are also clustered per RPFO to facilitate successive comparisons of our analysis results between and within countries.

Overall, the interviews with local stakeholders conducted under D1.3 "Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs" confirmed the relevance of some already mentioned factors. Communication and overall planning are aspects that can function as either determinants or barriers, depending on how they are treated (e.g., poor or effective provision of adequate information, feedback, and acknowledgement to participants, as well as the presence or absence of clear responsibilities, targets, and allocation of roles). Other aspects that influence individual motivations refer to the provision of incentives that can stimulate participation (e.g., monetary rewards) and the organisation of the project, in terms of transparency and structure (adequate power symmetries with limited top-down approaches and flexibility from all sides), which lead to reciprocal trust. Note that the aspects related to communication, transparency, and trust also emerged in D2.1 "Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes", although the interviews had a different scope there.

If we look at such evidence considering the specific national contexts, drives that appear recurrently relate to the structure of the project (its organisation and management) and the provision of incentives, although with different degrees of intensity. Focusing on the hindering factors, the scenario is slightly more dispersed in that there are no specific barriers that are perceived as such in all four contexts, which has been justified in light of the different socio-economic, cultural, and political frameworks.

Fruitful insights can also be drawn from the survey that took place under the framework of D1.3 "Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs". Among the expected benefits and drivers of individual participation, clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks have been highlighted across all four contexts, as well as the opportunity to receive continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project. Other recurring themes concern the importance of acknowledging each person's contribution (particularly in Greece and the Netherlands), for instance, through certificates, monetary rewards, public acknowledgement, or the possibility to see CSHs as chances to acquire knowledge and skills to be exploited for new career opportunities (the latter point also appeared in D2.1 "Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes"). The most common perceived barrier is instead a general scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups; other hindering factors relate to fears about the lack of time to participate (see also D2.1 "Co-Creation Workshop and its

outcomes”), the lack of required skills and knowledge to be involved, and how the contributions will be exploited by scientists and policy makers; other barriers are the lack of financial incentives and the feeling that the person belongs to a socio-demographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community.

2.3 Identification and selection of the engagement tools

Upon revising the theoretical literature and the evidence coming from the available INCENTIVE deliverables in terms of potential motivators and hindering factors, this Section focuses on the concrete instruments already implemented in other CS and QH stakeholders' experiences (Section 2.3.1) to identify the most common engagement tools and make a selection of those that are going to be tested in the following chapter (Section 2.3.2).

2.3.1 Main factors emerging from deliverables' results

Reviewing the literature that presents the evidence from previous projects, one of the aspects that stands out most relates to the wide range of tools that CS organisers employ to guarantee (or, at least, stimulate as much as possible) participants' active involvement. The use of these instruments, as well as their effectiveness, varies depending on the stage and the specific context in which they are utilised. To categorise such tools according to some criteria, we relied on the determinants behind co-production presented in Section 2.1.1 (i.e., ability and motivation).

Clearly, tools exist that may affect both factors. In that case, we categorised the tools based on their degree of impact. Another rationale followed below regards the timeline with respect to the progress of the CSH, gradually moving from those tools that are more relevant since the very beginning (to attract and engage) and going on with those that are more impactful in maintaining the community actively engaged.

Ability-related tools

When establishing a CSH, one of the first elements that shapes its future evolution relates to the definition of a physical and/or online space to meet (Schutz et al. 2019). This aspect deserves attention in that physical spaces may restrict accessibility for those with limited mobility, but online platforms may exclude certain categories of citizens who would be willing to participate but lack digital knowledge or resources. Thus, the selection of the space by the RPFO depends also on the target population to be involved, including a mix of physical and online meetings or ad hoc spaces for different groups of participants (Roman et al. 2020).

Another element that must be defined from the beginning and that can shape participants' ability to contribute is the adoption of facilitators (Compagnucci et al. 2021; Roman et al. 2020; Vohland et al. 2021), tasked with managing the practical aspects of the project and helping participants at the various stages.

One aspect that follows a similar debate to what was previously discussed regarding the space choice relates to the possibility to exploit meetings to engage citizens. Such meetings can be physical and/or online and take different formats: workshops (Asingizwe et al. 2021; Bellandi et al. 2021; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Golumbic et al. 2019; Roman et al. 2020; Schutz et al. 2019; Vallance et al. 2020; Vohland et al. 2021), focus groups and brainstorming sessions (Ampatzidou et al. 2018; Borghys et al. 2020; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Vlachos et al. 2021; Vohland et al. 2021), laboratories (Compagnucci et al. 2021), and so on. Once the format(s) is chosen, it is important to try to utilise informal settings (Vohland et al. 2021) and involve multidisciplinary teams (Compagnucci et al. 2021) to facilitate interaction.

Providing adequate supporting material is another aspect that improves individuals' ability to actively participate in a project: this can include information to be provided at the initial stages like protocols, guidelines, and tutorials on the tasks to be performed, toolkits and FAQs (Golumbic et al. 2019; Jackson et al. 2020; Vohland et al. 2021), or material that facilitates continuous involvement throughout the project, such as continuous training and other educational tools to learn from experience (Arienzo et al. 2021; August et al. 2019; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Dickinson et al. 2012; Golumbic et al. 2019; Satorras et al. 2020; Vlachos et al. 2021; Vohland et al. 2021).

When communicating with participants (either directly –physically or online– or indirectly –through supporting material), an element that can constitute a barrier to active participation relates to the language used: it must be inclusive, understandable, and common across subjects to facilitate the understanding of complex concepts (Vohland et al. 2021). Creating a common vocabulary may be an option (Bellandi et al. 2021).

Concerning the use of online tools, many contributions exist that provide suggestions on how to exploit them to maximise participation. When platforms are developed, they need to be user-friendly and associated with accessible tasks (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Golumbic et al. 2019). Social media is very useful in this framework as ways to facilitate participation, communication and interaction (Compagnucci et al. 2021); examples include online consultations/surveys, quizzes, e-voting, crowdsourcing, blogging, or hackathons (Ampatzidou et al. 2018; Arienzo et al. 2021; August et al. 2019; Borghys et al. 2020; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Fuster Morell and Senabre Hidalgo 2020; Golumbic et al. 2019; Oksman and Kulju 2017; Roman et al. 2020; Selada 2017; Vallance et al. 2020; Vohland et al. 2021). Considering what already emerged when discussing about meetings, it is preferable to combine online and physical tools (Vohland et al. 2021).

Motivation-related tools

Moving to instruments that influence individuals' motivation to interact, participate, and engage in CSHs, the available panorama that can be retrieved from previous experiences is also variegated. As before, the tools will be presented, starting from those that should be considered at the preliminary stages and then continuing with those that are more effective when it comes to sustaining over time the individual motivation to remain involved.

One of the first steps consists in identifying the topics of interest of the CSH. To foster individual motivation, such topics should be framed as local issues, and the potential actors have to be

convinced about the fact that their involvement in the CSH would have a concrete impact (Vohland et al. 2021). This approach should be developed by taking into consideration the concrete needs and interests of the potential participants, in light of their different backgrounds and levels of familiarity with the CS world (Asingizwe et al. 2020).

In parallel, an important step to stimulate motivation is to directly involve existing communities of interest, specific target groups, and individuals who have already participated in other CSHs (Arienzo et al. 2021; Golumbic et al. 2019; Roman et al. 2020).

After defining the topics of interest and the relevant population to involve, an important motivator to consider that is active during the engagement process relates to clearly defining the expectations on the participants and their tasks (Rotman et al. 2012; Vohland et al. 2021). As a certain level of expected effort can represent a barrier for those who are not particularly committed, CSHs can offer multiple ways or modular manners to facilitate participation with different levels of commitment (Fellnhofer 2017; Vohland et al. 2021).

When the project is officially in operation, a recurrent strategy employed in previous CS initiatives relates to gamification (Arienzo et al. 2021; Vohland et al. 2021), such as using board games, role playing (Ampatzidou et al. 2018), and other elements of fun and play to promote friendly competition and stimulate virtuous cycles of task completion (August et al. 2019; Greenhill et al. 2016). Examples could include the establishment of a “volunteer of the month” feature (Golumbic et al. 2019), or some periodic challenges (Dickinson et al. 2012).

Another strong and recurrent motivating factor is the acknowledgement of an individual’s contributions, which could be done through many different formats: Certificates, public acknowledgement, efforts’ recognition, encouragement, and emphasis on the uniqueness of an individual’s contribution (Arienzo et al. 2021; Arnkil et al. 2010; Asingizwe et al. 2020; August et al. 2019; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Dickinson et al. 2012; Lakomy et al. 2020; Rotman et al. 2012; Vohland et al. 2021).

Linked to this aspect, material rewards and monetary incentives serve as motivators (Asingizwe et al. 2020; McAdam et al. 2015). As they are usually intended as compensations for the time and efforts devoted, they do not constitute proper salaries. Given that their presence or absence can shape individual motivations to participate, it is suggested to clarify at the beginning whether monetary rewards will be provided or not (Asingizwe et al. 2020), as doing otherwise could create misunderstandings and disappointment, causing subsequent disengagement.

An important element that has to be taken into account throughout the entire duration of the project is communication, in terms of both providing continuous updates and giving the opportunity for the participants to interact directly with scientists. In the first case, it motivates citizens as they receive direct feedback about their work and thus become aware of the fact that their efforts are taken seriously (Arienzo et al. 2021; Asingizwe et al. 2021; August et al. 2019; Compagnucci et al. 2021; Golumbic et al. 2019; Roman et al. 2020; Vohland et al. 2021). Also, giving information about the project’s progress keeps the level of engagement active. In relation to the interaction with scientists, establishing discussion forums with them using an

understandable and informal framework and language raises participation and keeps interest high in the project (Asingizwe et al. 2021; Golumbic et al. 2019; Vohland et al. 2021).

Finally, to maintain citizens' engagement toward the end of the project, it is important to present information and data about the final results, if possible, via different channels (visual, textual, sound, etc.) and in user-friendly formats, like infographics. Also, data availability (open data), through easy-to-read formats, fosters motivation to keep working and be informed about the activities of the CSH (Golumbic et al. 2019; Selada 2017). Table 1 below summarises the presented ability and motivation-related tools.

Table 1: Most common tools

Tools	Main insights
Ability-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a space to meet, physical and/or online, being careful of those categories at risk exclusion. • Adopt facilitators. • Exploit physical and/or online meetings (workshops, focus groups and brainstorming sessions, laboratories), trying to set up informal settings and involve multidisciplinary teams to facilitate interaction. • Provide adequate supporting material (protocols, guidelines and tutorials, toolkits and FAQs, continuous training). • Adopt an inclusive and understandable language. • Exploit online tools, user-friendly and associated with accessible tasks.
Motivation-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frame identified topics as local issues and convince the potential actors about the concrete impact of their involvement in the CSH. • Involve existing communities of interest, specific target groups and individuals who have already participated in other CSHs. • Clearly define the expectations on the participants and their tasks and offer multiple ways or modular manners to participate with different levels of commitment. • Implement gamification strategies, such as board games, role playing and other elements of fun and play to promote friendly competition and stimulate virtuous cycles of task completion. • Acknowledge the contributions (e.g., through certificates, public acknowledgement, efforts' recognition). • Provide material rewards and monetary incentives, as compensations for the time and efforts devoted, clarifying their nature from the beginning.

- Communicate actively, both in terms of providing continuous updates and in terms of giving the possibility for the participants to interact directly with scientists.
- Present information and data about the final results, if possible, through different channels (visual, textual, sound, etc.) and in user-friendly formats, like infographics.

2.3.2 *Identification of the most appropriate testable tools*

Given the overview of the tools already employed in different projects and contexts, the next step of our process relates to the selection of those instruments to test their actual relevance among the local populations of the four CSHs. Although it would certainly be interesting to test all of them, such a great variety of identified tools forces us to make a selection according to some criteria.

From a theoretical perspective, our aim is to give proper emphasis to aspects pertaining to individual ability and/or motivation to link them according to the categories proposed by Alford (2002, 2009). Furthermore, the selection considers more practical aspects connected to the establishment of the CSHs. Then, the dimensions of interest are expected to focus on how the CSHs could organise their structure and operations. Another element worth considering is the impact the instrument to be tested could have depending on the category of participants (e.g., the relationship between elderly people and technology-related tools). The final identification of the tools considers the concrete possibility to test them (i.e., it is not simple to frame the impact of power asymmetry relationships on motivation in a linear and understandable way for the survey participants), and whether a relevant debate could be actually needed (e.g., providing material, listening to citizens' needs, or using an understandable language is supposed to be taken for granted).

In light of the described internal process (and to obtain reliable results), we decided to focus on six of the most exploited tools. They are equally distributed among those who are expected to influence participants' ability and motivation, and most of them are influential not only at the initial engagement stage but also for the entire duration of the project:

- The mode of involvement – One element of diversification across CSHs is how participants interact and actively participate (i.e., online, in person through meetings/workshops, and in person in the field). This tool belongs to the category of tools affecting individual ability to participate: the need to use technological devices to participate online could be a barrier for some categories of actors (e.g., seniors or less-educated individuals), while physical participation could pose similar issues for other segments of the population (e.g., people with physical disabilities).
- Expert facilitator – Some CSHs employ the presence of a team of facilitators, who help participants and clarify their doubts about how they can contribute (particularly at the beginning but also throughout the duration of the project). Identifying the relevance of

their presence/absence would be helpful for the RPFs to better organise the CSHs and their structure. As for the previous one, this tool also affects citizens' ability to participate.

- Continuous training – Another aspect that has already emerged in the review of CSHs is the possibility to provide participants with continuous training (in addition to the necessary instructions given when they join the project) and to learn from experience. Again, this possibility increases participants' ability to contribute, particularly concerning the quality of their contributions and their continuous engagement throughout the entire duration of the project. Nevertheless, as for the presence of expert facilitators, this could require additional resources; then, measuring its impact could provide useful recommendations for future CSHs.
- Incentive – Some of the CSHs reviewed considered the possibility to offer some types of monetary or non-monetary incentives for those who decided to contribute (e.g., small financial rewards, certificates, etc.). Thus, we decided to test the relevance of monetary incentives vs. non-monetary incentives vs. the absence of incentives. This tool is expected to influence individual motivation and participation throughout the project. As per the previous tools, the optimal choice might vary depending on specific categories of participants.
- Participants – Another source of heterogeneity relates to the pool of participants: while in some cases citizens and academics work together in the different stages of the project (e.g., decisions about the objectives, data collection, data analysis, etc.), in others, organisers and contributors work separately, with each having specific roles. An organisational aspect expected to affect individuals' willingness to participate concerns the ideal composition of the team (only with citizens, only with academics, a mixed composition of both).
- Public value/private interest – the sixth tool we selected relates to the final aim of the project and broadly pertains to the “topic of interest” mentioned as the first motivation-related tool. While CSHs usually focus on issues that are recognised as relevant by the entire local community, there exist initiatives that aim to deal with more general problematics, while others that provide concrete benefits particularly for those who participate. We included this dichotomy as the third factor influencing individual motivation, given that there might exist contexts in which public value-oriented projects are more effective than private value-based ones in engaging citizens and vice versa. This would also help CSHs in tailoring the CSH from a topic perspective.

3. Research design

After identifying the most promising tools, chapter 3 describes the methodological strategy exploited to collect the necessary data to develop relevant considerations. To test the importance of such tools, we decided to use a survey to go beyond the mere application of tools from previous experiences and concretely measure whether they are impactful or not. The survey has been distributed through online channels, which allowed us to maximise its diffusion and face the limitations consequent to the current COVID-19 pandemic. The complete questionnaire is presented in the Appendix; the questionnaire's content was developed by SDA Bocconi between December 2021 and February 2022, and it has been shared at different stages with the other partners of the INCENTIVE project for feedback and improvements. It comprises a mix of questions that cover socio-demographic aspects (to get a general overview of the respondents' main characteristics), previous information and experience regarding CS, relevance of the tools, willingness to participate in future projects, and topics of interest. In this way, we have been able to not only identify the importance of the tested instruments but also collect additional information on potential participants' preferences and priorities.

To concretely measure the impact of the chosen tools from a more technical perspective, we relied on a conjoint section approach, a method that allows measuring the individual's degree of engagement, presenting two alternative CSHs and asking the participant to choose the preferred one. The two scenarios are completely identical except for the levels of the chosen tools, which combination differs at random from participant to participant. The importance of such randomised allocation of different levels of the tools under analysis lies in the fact that it allows us to directly infer causality: the randomisation process implies that any difference emerging in terms of relative importance of a certain tool or of a specification of that tool is dependent on such process.

Instead of distributing the questionnaire at the Behavioural Lab of SDA Bocconi, we opted for a cross-country analysis. In this way, we have been able to involve representative samples of citizens directly from the four countries in which the CSHs are being established, rather than recruiting only one sample from Italy. This allowed us to include in the analysis the impact of cultural aspects as potential influencing factors of the individual preferences in terms of tools and their levels. Furthermore, the current pandemic restrictions would have limited the possibility to recruit and gather potential participants in a physical space. To recruit participants from the four countries of interest (the Netherlands, Spain, Greece, and Lithuania) we contacted Luc.id, a private company specialised in recruiting survey volunteers at an international level. While the original text was written in English, at the distribution stage, the participants received the survey questionnaire in their own native language (Dutch, Spanish, Greek, or Lithuanian). The data collection process took place in March 2022; the survey has been distributed through Qualtrics, a platform specialised in structuring online questionnaires, which also provides a wide array of analytical features (including the conjoint analysis utilised in this deliverable).

4. Findings

Before starting the analysis of the evidence that characterises the survey, some comments about the recruited samples and their representativeness are required.

Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics

Individual characteristics		Total
Gender	Male	47.72%
	Female	52.00%
	Other/not specified	0.28%
Age	18-19	5.42%
	20-24	17.21%
	25-29	14.54%
	30-34	14.54%
	35-39	13.78%
	40-44	11.21%
	45-49	10.46%
	50-54	5.61%
	55-59	4.37%
	60-64	2.95%
Education	Less than Diploma	4.66%
	Diploma	38.21%
	Bachelor	37.93%
	Master	14.36%
	Post-Master	3.04%
	Other/not specified	1.90%
Main educational background	Arts/literature	7.41%
	Natural sciences	6.37%
	Health sciences	12.45%
	Engineering/construction	14.07%
	Architecture/urban planning	2.47%
	Economics/finance	22.24%
	Social sciences	11.22%
	Other/not specified	23.76%
	Student	14.03%
	Employment	Worker
Entrepreneur		7.32%
Unemployed		13.12%
Retired		1.62%
Other/not specified		3.52%
N		1052

As presented in Table 2, 1052 participants completed the questionnaire. The overall sample is evenly distributed across males and females; in terms of age, it is possible to see how the majority of the participants is less than 40 years old (in line with the expectations related to the use of an online instrument). In terms of general education, the modal value ranges between high school diploma and bachelor’s degree; the main educational background is heterogeneous as well, with a considerable number of residual topics classifiable as “other/not specified”. Looking at the employment status, most of the respondents are currently working, with around 14% of students and 13% unemployed. Coherently with what found when looking at the age brackets, the number of retired people is relatively low; this can be explained in light of the fact that we wanted to concentrate on those individuals pertaining to the active population (18-64 years old). Note that, for the employment question, we allowed respondents to pick more than one option to avoid forcing them to choose in case their situation was unclear (e.g., working students); this explains why the overall sum is greater than 100%. Although potentially relevant for our study, no specific questions have been included about categorisations into the QH stakeholders’ framework, as this would have created confusion among the participants (i.e., everyone pertains to the “citizen” categorisation). The same table with the specifications for the four countries can be found in the Appendix (Table A1).

Another introductory aspect that is worth considering relates to their relationship with CS-related topics. In particular, we were interested in understanding what is their previous knowledge about the CS world, if they had already participated in other CS initiatives, their propensity to participate in future “interesting” CSHs and their topics of interest. Table 3 presented below shows the current panorama according to these aspects.

Table 3: CS-related questions per country

CS aspects		Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Previous knowledge of CS	Yes	58.8%	45.8%	47.7%	53.8%
	No	41.2%	54.2%	52.3%	46.2%
Previous participation on CS projects	Yes	12.3%	9.3%	17%	13%
	No	87.7%	90.7%	83%	87%
Probability to participate in "interesting" CS projects	Absolutely not	1.6%	10.2%	7.3%	4.1%
	Probably not	6.6%	14.4%	11%	6%
	Maybe	39.3%	42.4%	42.7%	29.8%
	Probably	38.9%	22.9%	30%	42.1%
	Absolutely	16.7%	10.2%	9%	18%
Topics of interest of a hypothetical CS project	Health	11.3%	12.6%	17.1%	11.6%
	Environmental sciences	7.5%	5.4%	5.7%	8.6%
	Energy and sustainability	8.1%	10.2%	9.2%	9.8%
	Public administration and policy	6%	6%	5.5%	4.3%
	Information technologies	7.5%	8.7%	5%	6.1%
	Circular economy	6.3%	3%	3.4%	5.1%
	Communication sciences	5.6%	7.8%	5.1%	4.8%
	Transportation and mobility	4%	6.9%	6.8%	7.6%
	Human media interaction	6.6%	6.3%	3.4%	5.2%
	Educational sciences	8.6%	4.5%	7.1%	7.9%
Urban development and planning	3.2%	3.9%	5.5%	4.6%	

	Culture	8.2%	6.9%	7.8%	7.8%
	Civil rights	10.9%	7.5%	8.5%	6.1%
	Social welfare	6%	9%	9%	10.3%
	Other	0.3%	1.5%	1%	0.4%
N		318	118	300	316

In terms of previous knowledge, we can see, in all the four contexts, around half of the sample already knows about citizen science (at least, they already heard something about that in the past), with higher previous knowledge in Greece and Spain (58.8% and 53.8% respectively) compared to the Netherlands and Lithuania (47.7% and 45.8%).

Also, previous participation in CSHs is quite comparable across countries, as it ranges between 9.3% (Lithuania) and 17% (Netherlands). It is interesting to note how, although the Greek sample showed the highest percentage of prior knowledge, then the previous participation rate is relatively low. Contrary, in the Netherlands there is relatively high participation, both in absolute terms and with respect to those that are already aware of the CS concept.

Moving to the willingness to participate in future CSHs of their interest, we can see how the most reluctant ones are the Lithuanians (24.6% of them would not participate, absolutely or probably), which is a percentage quite in contrast compared to the other countries (18.3% for the Netherlands, 10.1% for Spain and 8.2% for Greece, which shows the highest percentage of enthusiasts from this perspective). If we concentrate on the positive framing (i.e., those who would participate, absolutely or probably), we can find consistent results, with the Spanish and Greek samples that show the highest willingness to participate (60.1% and 55.6%, respectively).

Finally, referring to which topics would be “interesting” to them, we exploited the list of themes already developed in previous deliverables for better comparability, integrating it with further potential areas of interest. Note that, also in this case, we allowed for more options to be chosen. The main topic of interest, probably unsurprisingly in light of the current pandemic, relates to the health sector in all four countries. If we look at the five most chosen themes, health and energy are the only areas that recur in all the contexts. Then, there exist other recurring topics, like social welfare, civil rights, education and culture.

Moving to the aspects of main interest, the following figures focus on the analysis of the six chosen tools, presenting the relevance shares together with the optimal bundle that maximises individual participation within each country. The former concept describes the relative importance of each tool in percentage terms in the decision-making process about joining or not a CSH. The latter one corresponds to the item of a tool that maximises participation in an “ideal” CSH. The same information presented below can be found in Table A2 in the Appendix.

Figure 1: Relevance of the six tools - Greece

Figure 2: Relevance of the six tools - Lithuania

Figure 3: Relevance of the six tools - the Netherlands

Figure 4: Relevance of the six tools - Spain

The information presented in Figures 1-4 shows the relevance shares expressed by the respondents from each country (additional information can be found in the Appendix in Table A2). In particular, they represent how much that tool influenced respondents' choice between scenarios during the conjoint Section of the survey. The names of the tools have been synthesised to foster the overall readability and refer, respectively, to how participants are going to be

involved (online, in presence through workshops, in presence in the field), the presence or absence of expert facilitators and continuous training activities throughout the project, the presence or absence of monetary and non-monetary incentives, the composition of the working teams (mixed or with academics or citizens only) and the general coverage of the project (whether focused more on generating public value or creating value for the private interest).

In line with the previous literature that expressed how providing incentives is relevant in terms of fostering motivation (either monetary rewards or non-monetary ones), this is the element that mostly affects individual motivation in all four countries. There exists some heterogeneity (from 29.8% in Spain to 48.2% in the Netherlands), but its importance with respect to the other tools is clear as the percentages imply how, depending on the country, their presence alone impacted almost half of the entire decision process. Higher variance across countries emerges when we take a look at the other tools that influence individual decisions. While in Greece the second and third tools are the mode of involvement (27%) and the nature of participants (22.2%), in Lithuania these are mode of involvement (29%) and continuous training (11.2%), in the Netherlands nature of participants (16.3%) and continuous training (11.6%) and in Spain mode of involvement (18%) and nature of participants (15.7%). In addition to the heterogeneity in terms of tools relevance, also the percentages show marked variability, in particular if we look at the extreme cases of the Netherlands (where incentives have an absolute role) and Spain (where all the tools somehow contribute to the final decision). Furthermore, it is worth mentioning how, in all four contexts, the presence/absence of a facilitator and the focus on public value/private interest never appear among the top three relevant tools. Overall, it seems that the final decisions are more dependent on those factors that influence individual motivation with respect to those that affect the ability to participate.

Another theme of interest relates to the “optimal package” of tools, i.e., the first choices (specified in the figures for each tool) for what concerns the different levels within a tool. The first element that emerges is that in all four countries the preferred mode of involvement is online, the presence of continuous training throughout the project is appreciated, as well as the possibility to get some types of monetary rewards. Such information is presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Optimal tools to use for engagement in CSHs

Tools	
Mode of involvement	Online
Continuous training	Presence
Incentive	Monetary

Then, if we look at the “deviations” from the most chosen levels, we can see how in the Netherlands citizens express their willingness to be involved in teams composed of only academics (excluding the presence of other citizens). The Lithuanian context shows other interesting specificities as, in this case, participants have low interest in the presence of expert facilitators, while they seem to prefer projects more focused on the private interest sphere with

respect to those that concentrate on creating public value. These anomalies could be justified in light of the overall reluctance towards CS (already emerged in the previous deliverables) together with the general low interest in CS initiatives (see the low percentages found in terms of CS knowledge and previous participation). Again, such information is summarised below (Table 5).

Table 5: Country-specific tools of engagement

Tools	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Expert facilitator	Presence	Absence	Presence	Presence
Participants	Mixed	Mixed	Academics	Mixed
Public value/Private interest	Public	Private	Public	Public

Once the main results were identified through a cross-country comparison, the next four Sections provide an overview of the single countries, shedding light on what generated the “optimal packages”. The next Sections show the evidence in a more descriptive way, while Chapter 6 will provide more practical insights and indications for the local RPOs (e.g., Section 6.3).

4.1 Greece

The next Figure provides an overview of the specific preferences shown by the Greek sample.

Figure 5: Preference shares for each level of the six tools - Greece

Looking at the mode of involvement, the online option has the majority of the preferences, although this choice may have been affected by the current pandemic situation. Given that also workshops received remarkable attention, coherently with the evolution of the Covid-19 pandemic, there could be some discussion about providing a mix of involvement strategies. Regarding the expert facilitators, although we already saw from Figure 1 that this tool is not influent for the final decision, we can see how there is a clear preference for their presence; the same conclusions can be done for the presence of continuous training. Moving to those factors that affect individual motivation, the impact of receiving any type of incentive is strongly driven by the possibility to receive a small monetary reward; then, the weight that Greek respondents put on the nature of the participants (see Figure 1) is driven by their willingness to interact with a mixed group of citizens and academic researchers. Finally, for what concerns the dichotomy between projects that focus more on public value or private interest, again, we can see how a marked preference towards activities that generate value for the community is not translated into a factor that concretely affects the individual decisions when it comes to choosing among different projects.

4.2 Lithuania

As for the previous Section, the following Figure 6 presents the preference shares related to the Lithuanian context.

Figure 6: Preference shares for each level of the six tools – Lithuania

Starting from the mode of involvement, we can see very similar percentages compared to the Greek context, which means that the same conclusions and suggestions can also be done here. As mentioned, when commenting on the peculiarities of each specific country, one of the anomalies that emerge when looking at the Lithuanian context relates to the preferences for the absence of an expert facilitator. Nevertheless, as the shares are quite evenly distributed (and given that overall, this tool has a very marginal impact on individual choices), it is not possible to draw specific suggestions about this aspect. In terms of continuous training the situation is clearer, both in terms of preference shares and relevance with respect to the other tools. Also in this case, the incentive tool shows the highest relevance, driven by the preference for monetary rewards. Nevertheless, the internal preferences are more homogeneous if compared to the Greek ones, with an interesting higher preference towards no incentives at all with respect to non-monetary rewards. Also, in terms of participants we can see a preferred option but, at the same time, a quite homogeneous distribution across the three alternatives. Concluding with the choice between projects that focus more on public value or private interest, we can take the same inputs as for the expert facilitator presence: the two options show very similar percentages, and this tool is the least relevant of the six.

4.3 The Netherlands

Moving to the Dutch sample, Figure 7 presents the evidence for each tool and level.

Figure 7: Preference shares for each level of the six tools – the Netherlands

Looking again at the mode of involvement, interestingly, the online mode remains the preferred option but loses preferences significantly. In fact, it is almost equalised by the involvement in person in the field, which is the least preferred option both in Greece and Lithuania, and the sum of the two in-person options overcomes the online one. As for Greece, we can see similar share preferences for the presence of an expert facilitator and continuous training, even though in the Dutch context both have slightly stronger impacts on the overall decision to participate in a certain CSH (7.6% versus 2.2% for the facilitators and 11.6% versus 5.1% for the continuous training in Figures 1 and 3). Coherently with what already found, small monetary rewards have a relevant role; similarly to Lithuania, individuals prefer no rewards at all with respect to non-monetary ones. Moving to the perfect mix of participants, there is a strong balance between those who prefer to work with only academics and those who enjoy a mix with citizens. The most remarkable aspect is that they are not interested in interacting only with other citizens. Finally, Dutch respondents are more interested in projects that focus on public value. This willingness is confirmed by the fact that this tool has a markedly higher share with respect to Greece and Lithuania.

4.4 Spain

Analogously as before, Figure 8 presents the evidence specific to the Spanish context.

Figure 8: Preference shares for each level of the six tools – Spain

The first aspect that deserves attention is the highest percentage share given to the online mode of involvement, if compared with the other countries. Strong interest has also been given to the presence of an expert facilitator and continuous training throughout the project, which is also confirmed by the quite significant impact on the final decision (respectively, 14.3% and 12.3% in Figure 4). Monetary incentives play a dominant role again, with the non-monetary rewards that gain preferences with respect to the complete absence. There is a lack of interest in participating with teams composed only of citizens although, in the Spanish case, there is a strong preference for a mix of academics and citizens. In terms of preferences between projects that focus on public value versus private interests, the Spanish sample shows the highest interest in the first approach, both in terms of preference shares and for what concerns the impact of this tool on the final decision to engage in a CSH.

4.5 Focus on specific categories

In line with the aim of this deliverable, the next Section develops a similar analysis to what has been done before, focusing on some subcategories i.e., women, seniors, and people with low levels of education. The objective is to identify any relevant differences in terms of drivers, to think about ad hoc solutions to guarantee adequate inclusion and diversity across genders and subgroups typically at risk of exclusion.

4.5.1 Women

The first focus aims at identifying whether relevant differences exist when considering the subpopulation of women, given the potential gender heterogeneities in terms of participation (e.g., Lakomy et al. 2020). The scope is to understand if women’s preferences about the analysed tools correspond to the general populations they belong to and if there are differences between women from different countries. In line with the previous analysis, we present the relevance of each tool together with the level that composes the optimal bundle and maximises participation. The information is presented below in Figures 9-12.

Figure 9: Relevance of the six tools in Greece - Women

Figure 10: Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania – Women

Figure 11: Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands – Women

Figure 12: Relevance of the six tools in Spain - Women

Comparing the importance given to the tools by women and the overall population they belong to (Figures 1-4), there are no significant divergences, as all the differences that emerge are within two percentage points. Consequently, both the discussion about the relevant tools that shape the individual decision to engage in CSHs and the cross-country comparisons developed above apply also to the women subgroup. Similarly, looking at the optimal packages, we can see how women from all four contexts are aligned with the preferences of the overall population (Tables 4 and 5), with a perfect correspondence of the “ideal” CSH between the two samples for each country.

4.5.2 Seniors

Another category of participants that deserves particular attention is constituted by seniors, defined as those aged 50 years old or more. For different reasons, their involvement can be critical; potential barriers linked to age could be limited technological knowledge or limited mobility.

Figure 13: Relevance of the six tools in Greece - Seniors

Figure 14: Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania - Seniors

Figure 15: Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands – Seniors

Figure 16: Relevance of the six tools in Spain – Seniors

Following the same structure of the previous section, the first comparison considers the relevance of the six tools in shaping the individual decisions to join and engage in a CSH. The first element that we should underline is the small sample, in particular for some countries (Lithuania and Greece). Then, comparing Figures 1-4 with Figures 13-16, some slight differences can be

highlighted: looking at those changes of two percentage points or more, the Greek subsample shows an increased relevance for the mode of involvement (+4.9%) and a decreased interest for the incentives (-2.4%). For the Lithuanian pool we can see higher importance given to the expert facilitators (+2.8%, although the percentage has limited reliability given the very small sample), while for the Netherlands seniors give even more weight to incentives (+3.6%). For what concerns Spain, there is a strong alignment with the preferences of the overall population.

Moving to the optimal bundle of a hypothetical CSH, the Greek subsample shows a higher preference towards only academics as part of their working team, instead of a mix with citizens witnessed for the general population. Still considering the potential impact of the small subsample, in Lithuania we can highlight the absence of continuous training, in addition to the absence of facilitators already found for the entire national sample. In addition, Dutch participants show a particular interest in activities in the field, while for Spain there is total comparability with the full national sample.

4.5.3 Participants with low levels of education

This Section is dedicated to the preferences of the last subgroup of our interest i.e., people characterised by low levels of education (with a high-school diploma or less). For instance, these participants may experience difficulties with technology-related issues; not considering their needs could result in a technical barrier that excludes them from actively participating.

Figure 17: Relevance of the six tools in Greece – People with low levels of education

Figure 18: Relevance of the six tools in Lithuania - People with low levels of education

Figure 19: Relevance of the six tools in the Netherlands - People with low levels of education

Figure 20: Relevance of the six tools in Spain - People with low levels of education

Comparing the evidence from Figures 17-20 with Figures 1-4, what emerges is an almost identical impact of the six tools on the individual decisions. There exist very slight differences, that never overcome two percentage points. Then, as for the women subsample, also when considering citizens with low levels of education, we can draw the same conclusions developed for the entire national samples, suggesting that the differences that emerge from the analysis depend mainly on national/cultural contexts that affect the four populations in their entirety, compared to those more nuanced that take place within countries.

Also the optimal bundles are very similar to those presented in Tables 4 and 5, as they are exactly the same for Greece, the Netherlands and Spain, while in Lithuania there is a preference for the participation of only academics instead of a mix of academics and citizens.

5. Discussion

From our research, it clearly emerged that the preferred mode of involvement in CSHs in all four countries and across all specific categories of population groups is **online, through a digital platform**. This preference is to be expected due to the convenience of the timing, place and other aspects of participation. Moreover, it can be largely attributed to the massive service digitalisation trend that has made its appearance globally due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which gave an unprecedented boost to the development of new co-creation platforms, tools and applications, rendering, in several cases, online participation a one-way (the only) choice. It should be kept in mind, however, that the great majority of the respondents have no prior experience of participating in CSHs, which might make it difficult to appreciate the value of the face-to-face co-creation experience and as well as the in-situ creation experience.

The mixed results regarding the differences in the preference for the presence or absence of **an expert facilitator** may be related to differences in the affinity of the respondents to CS as a way of doing science. In developing our conclusions about this tool, we should also account for the finding that this tool has a very low relevance score in all countries (Figures 1-4), meaning that it has a very limited effect on the decision-making process.

Further down the line, we found that in all four countries citizens appreciate the availability of **continuous training** and **appropriate tools** as a means to facilitate the implementation of a CSH. This is, of course, a sense-making option: the vast diversity and variability of CSH types and disciplines render basic training, the availability of appropriate tools and the familiarisation of the participants with previous experiences and best practices a necessity for any CSH. It is noteworthy that the respondents are capable of apprehending the value of training, despite their not so extensive knowledge of CS and their even more limited prior experience from participating in CSHs. Training is an aspect of CS performing that we, at INCENTIVE, have also identified as a critical component of performing excellent CS and we have incorporated it into the activities of the CSHs.

The significance of the availability of an **incentive** in the form of a small monetary reward for contribution was arguably the most vigorous and consistent finding of our research. In all countries, and across all special population groups, there was unanimity that a small monetary incentive may catalyse participation. Non-monetary awards are also appreciated, although to a much lesser extent. The high relevance of this tool in all countries (Figures 1-4) enforces the suggestion that participation in CS would benefit greatly from the offering of incentives, monetary or not. Considering this conclusion, our suggestion is that all RPFOS should consider which awards, prizes or kinds of recognition they could offer to the members of their CS community in order to incentivise and thence increase participation.

The variability of our findings regarding the **participants'** mix in terms of profiles is also very interesting. While in three out of the four countries there is a prevalent opinion that CSHs should be implemented by a mixed group of citizens and academic researchers, this was not the case for the Netherlands. There, the notion that CSHs are best implemented with the participation only of academic researchers was prevalent. Perhaps, this can be attributed to the fact that the

Netherlands have a strong tradition in co-creation, co-design and other forms and modes of collaborative production.

Regarding the last tool, that of **public value versus private interest**, in three of the four countries it is believed that CS activities should first and foremost generate value for the community. By doing so, there is a higher chance that citizens will participate in CSHs. In contrast, in Lithuania prevailed a more individualistic attitude, by which CS should first satisfy individual needs and then generate value for the community. However, this finding should not be regarded as of increased significance and value to our present work due to two reasons. First, the difference in the preferences of Lithuanian respondents was not so important. Second, the tool altogether has a relatively limited influence on the decision to participate in CSHs, based on our findings (Figures 1-4).

6. Guidelines to incentivise and engage Quadruple Helix stakeholders in Citizen Science Hubs

This section of the manual aims to develop a manual for citizen science community building, and it introduces approaches, tools and methods that can be applied for effective engagement activities. It may be used when setting up an RRI-oriented citizen science community, including incentivisation tools.

The guidelines of this section can introduce CSH staff to the breath of consideration to take into account as they plan their stakeholder engagement initiatives. It addresses the following questions:

- What is citizen engagement?
- Under which conditions does citizens' engagement enhance CSH activities?
- How to use the incentivisation tools?
- How to develop an engagement plan?

6.1 What is citizen engagement in CSH?

Citizen engagement in CSH is the active involvement of individual citizens in scientific research, policy and program development. "Active" engagement implies an active role in defining issues, considering solutions, contributing with their own effort, knowledge and resources. Citizen engagement can take place at various stages of the establishment and implementation of a CSH. There are generally four phases identified (Nabatchi et al. 2017):

- **Co-commissioning.** Citizen engagement in co-commissioning refers to activities aimed at strategically identifying and prioritising the scope of the CSH. Their contributions shape what needs to be delivered, to whom and what outcomes shall be achieved through a CSH.
- **Co-design.** Citizen engagement in co-design refers to activities that incorporate the experience of citizens and communities into the creation, planning and arrangement of a CSH. It offers an "outside-in" perspective to design CSH for the use and benefit of individuals.
- **Co-delivery.** Citizen engagement in co-production refers to joint activities between CSH staff and lay actors that are sued to directly implement activities of the CSH.
- **Co-assessment.** Citizen engagement in co-assessment refers to monitoring and evaluating the CSH activities. It includes performance-related activities undertaken by CSH staff and lay actors. It usually takes a retrospective nature, it is oriented towards the past, related to activities that already took place to inform future CSH initiatives.

In general, citizen engagement and stakeholder engagement activities range from the inclusion of citizen representatives on steering committees to the development of partnerships with targeted community groups to the employment of citizens that lived the experience relevant for

performing the CSH (i.e., mental health patients, trained and hired to support care and research activities). There is no one way to engage citizens and other stakeholders in CSH. The scope, needs and activities of different CSH may lead to different engagement practices and experiences.

However, it should be noted that including stakeholders in CSH's organisation, planning, decision-making, implementation of activities and evaluation requires adequate capacity, the understanding of roles and clear communication. Citizens and stakeholders, in general, bring their values and ideologies and new voices to the CSH. CSH staff should be trained and open to engage in open communication and inform citizens of the expectations they have to generate informed participation that shall lead to participatory approaches to achieving CSH goals.

6.2 Under which conditions does citizen engagement enhance CSH activities?

Citizen and stakeholder engagement in CSH adds value to the program by recognising their valuable contribution to the CSH activities in terms of ability, resources and motivation to serve not just personal but also community and societal related goals.

In general, citizens' and stakeholders' engagement facilitate mutual learning and understanding. In turn, this may enhance openness, trust and transparency. However, in order to proactively contribute to the CSH activities, stakeholder engagement has to be carefully planned and governed.

It requires the right approach to their engagement, to empower them to provide valuable input into the development and direction of new initiatives and priorities. A wide range of tools exists to foster citizen engagement; some are more aligned with their expectations, as will be described in the next paragraph.

Our survey shows that citizens prefer the online mode of interaction to stay engaged in CSH activities. Therefore, an effective onboarding may have to make sure that citizens have the right skill set to contribute to the CSH activities. Citizens contributing to CHS should have and consolidate two main types of competencies and capacity: digital capacity and skills as well as technical competencies on the topic of the CSH.

CHS should ensure the proper training to all stakeholders to support knowledge development and to ensure their full participation across all phases of CSH activities.

To stimulate effective engagement, CSH should ensure citizen representation across all activities ranging from the setting of priorities and decision-making and research policy settings. Citizen participation on CHS boards shall foster openness and transparency in decision-making. Their involvement in CSH plans, strategies and policies may facilitate shared goals and ensure continuous support. CHS should also embrace the opportunity to encourage researchers to engage with citizens to establish the research questions.

6.3 How to use the incentivisation tools

In the next tables, we discuss each tool assessed and provide a description of the tool, suggestions on when to apply it, strengths and weaknesses of applying it and suggestions on how to apply it.

6.3.1 Mode of involvement

Mode of involvement	
Description of the incentivisation tool	<p>The mode of involvement refers to how participants interact and actively participate: online, in-person through meetings/workshops, or in-person directly in the field (e.g., when their role is focused on data collection).</p> <p>The choice of the modality can be defined as an incentive to participate in that, depending on the final decision, different categories of stakeholders could perceive it as a stimulating factor or as a barrier to participation.</p> <p>Our test shows that the online mode of involvement is the most preferred one in all four countries; given the importance of the involvement tool (in particular for Greece and Spain, see Figures 1-4), CSHs should carefully evaluate how to proceed from this perspective.</p>
When to apply it	<p>The online mode of delivery is mainly applicable to three phases of the CSH initiatives: Co-commissioning, Co-design and Co-assessment.</p> <p>Its adoption in co-production depends on the type of activities required.</p> <p>Please be aware that it may segregate selected stakeholders as the elderly, the low educated individuals and the ones with no digital skills. The online mode of delivery may be joined with in-presence modes of delivery to prevent this risk.</p>
Strengths and weaknesses	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Consensus and active participation. The online mode of involvement showed high consensus among potential participants from all countries; then, this strategy could be effective in recruiting a remarkable number of participants.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Invest in stakeholders' digital culture. The need to use technological devices to participate online could be a barrier for some categories of actors that may be more comfortable with in-person interactions (e.g., seniors, as witnessed for instance in the Netherlands). This requires investment in the digital culture of</p>

	<p>participants and onboarding training to use the online platform for citizen engagement in the CSH.</p> <p>Physical barriers. Physical participation could bring similar issues to actual onboarding for other segments of the population (e.g., people with physical disabilities, particularly when the venue is not easily reachable by foot or with public transportation). CSH should put in place all conditions to minimise this risk.</p>
<p>How to apply it</p>	<p>Online Workshops. The organisation of the workshop should address the stakeholder composition to favour mixed stakeholder groups.</p> <p>Online workshop is the second most preferred modality for Greece, Spain and Lithuania, while in the Netherlands there exists a higher preference for supporting the CSH directly in the field. Such preferences are also confirmed when focusing on women, citizens with low levels of education and senior participants; in particular, Dutch citizens pertaining to the latter category showed their highest preference for working in the field.</p> <p>Gamification and persuasion methods. To ensure continuous online engagement, younger stakeholders tend to appreciate gamification as a mode of continuous engagement, whereas older stakeholders' continuous participation.</p>

6.3.2 Expert facilitator

Expert facilitator	
Description of the incentivisation tool	<p>Expert facilitators are figures that help participants throughout the entire involvement in the CSH activities. They clarify any doubts stakeholders may have about how they can contribute (particularly during the onboarding session), providing technical support for the data collection process and managing online and in presence events (e.g., producing and providing relevant material in advance). An expert facilitator also aims at smoothening the relationship between formal CSH staff and external stakeholders by creating a common glossary.</p>
When to apply it	<p>The expert facilitator is essential in the Co-commissioning, Co-design and Co-production phase. It is also very useful in the Co-assessment phase to support the stakeholders with technical competencies about the evaluation process.</p> <p>The presence of an expert facilitator is preferred in Greece, Spain and the Netherlands, with a particular appreciation by the Spanish sample (both in terms of the impact of this tool on the final decisions and considering the preferences of presence versus absence). No particular heterogeneities are found looking at the analysed subsamples.</p> <p>The Lithuanian context is characterised by a general lack of interest or trust in this figure. If we look at the willingness expressed by the general population and the three subsamples, there is a slight preference towards its absence; this is particularly remarked by the elderly population, but the very small subsample (7 individuals) does not allow us to draw solid conclusions.</p>
Strengths and weaknesses	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Onboarding and engagement. Expert facilitators can be very useful because their work as facilitators clarifies and simplifies participants' tasks, both from a more theoretical and practical perspective (e.g., providing additional material or clarifying doubts about the data collection tasks or giving practical information about how to reach the venue).</p> <p>Balanced workload. Their presence also simplifies the work of Citizen Scientists and the entire staff working in the CSH, as they represent the point of connection with all the stakeholders and reduces the overall workload, allowing the administrative staff and the project organisers to better focus on the activities rather than on practical and technical issues.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Trust. Expert facilitators may contribute to stakeholders' engagement actively if there is a trust-based relationship among all key actors involved in the CSH. The Lithuanian context showed a general lack of</p>

	<p>interest in this opportunity which could derive from low levels of trust. These preferences suggest a reflection on how facilitators present themselves and how this could negatively affect participation: for instance, a too paternalistic approach towards the problems experienced by participants could be perceived as treating them as people who are not able to perform the tasks and need continuous help. This could provoke disappointment and discouragement and eventually dropouts from the project.</p>
<p>How to apply it</p>	<p>Set up proper governance. RPFOS should organise their internal structure in order to include in the CSH teams the expert facilitators.</p> <p>Allocate resources. Given that, depending on the available budget of the CSH, hiring a team of facilitators could be a relevant cost for the project, being aware of citizens' preferences becomes fundamental in the final choice of implementing or not this engagement tool. The suggestion is to exploit expert facilitators in all the four CSHs. Nevertheless, if their presence is going to relevantly affect the overall budget of the project, external facilitators could be involved only during the first part of the project, relying on the voluntary activity of particularly active participants in the continuation of the project.</p>

6.3.3 Invest in continuous training for stakeholders

Continuous training	
<p>Description of the incentivisation tool</p>	<p>Training refers to equipping citizens and other stakeholders with the skills and knowledge to understand the functioning of the initiative, the technical background needed to actively contribute to the scope and mission.</p> <p>Continuous training refers to the possibility to get further training throughout the project in addition to the necessary instructions given when they join the project, and to learn from experience.</p> <p>This possibility fosters participants' ability to contribute and strengthens the quality of their contributions. Examples of continuous training relate to periodic meetings and/or courses or to additional material that can be delivered and personalised depending on the tasks of the participants and on the current quality and quantity of their contributions.</p>
<p>When to apply it</p>	<p>Training is essential as an onboarding activity for any of the Co-commissioning, Co-design, Co-production and Co-assessment phases. It is also very useful in the Co-assessment phase to support the stakeholders with technical competencies about the evaluation process.</p> <p>The presence of continuous training showed general appreciation across all four countries, with an interesting (although not particularly high) impact on citizens' final decisions to join expressed in the Conjoint section. In particular, this tool had a limited impact on the</p>

	<p>Greek context. This appreciation is also confirmed by the preferences shares, with the Spanish sample that showed the highest interest. Also looking at the population subsamples, the evidence is confirmed almost everywhere.</p>
<p>Strengths and weaknesses</p>	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Increased engagement. Continuous training is expected to increase participants' involvement, as they receive continuous stimuli to learn and contribute and they feel empowered by seeing how their contributions evolve through the project.</p> <p>Furthermore, receiving periodic training and stimuli works also as a reminder to participate, in particular for those who participate occasionally or who stopped contributing because they have been left behind for any reason in the learning process. As a consequence, this tool increases the effort put in by participants, both in terms of quantity and quality of the contributions provided for their tasks.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Burden and efforts. The main risk to be avoided when implementing continuous training opportunities lies in the fact that such training activities could become too burdening: this can happen if they are too many, too frequent, too difficult to understand or if their participation is de facto compulsory to keep participating and contributing to the project. If this risk becomes real, this could lead to the unintended consequence of lowering citizens' participation due to lack of time, decreasing interest, perception that a voluntary activity is becoming a job and lack of skills in case the training opportunities constitute a step towards more difficult tasks.</p>
<p>How to apply it</p>	<p>Training should be of two types: motivational and technical. Motivational training aims at sharing the values of the CSH; technical training aims at empowering citizens with the proper competencies to support the CSH activities, including digital capacity, research and project management skills and technical competencies related to the scope of the CSH.</p> <p>The suggestion is to propose continuous training in all the four CSHs, given the general preference towards their presence both looking at the general populations and at the specific subsamples of our interest.</p>

6.3.4 Monetary and non-monetary Incentives

Incentive	
Description of the incentivisation tool	<p>Monetary incentives consist of small sums of money to compensate participants for their time and efforts devoted. They are small in that they are not intended as substitutes for a regular salary, given that their contributions are not defined by any contract and are completely voluntary. Examples of these sums typically consist of reimbursement (if the CSH venue is particularly far or not easily accessible) or prizes linked to the number of tasks performed.</p> <p>Non-monetary incentives relate to awards that vary depending on the rationale behind them: for instance, they can be certificates (linked to the participation in training courses) or different types of acknowledgements (e.g., public acknowledgement in front of their peers and scientists, "volunteer of the month" feature).</p> <p>The absence of incentives means that participation is completely free.</p>
When to apply it	<p>Incentives can be used across all CSH phases. However, the choice of the proper incentive (monetary and non-monetary) may depend upon the characteristics of the stakeholders, their priorities and the CSH's requirements.</p> <p>Our test shows a strong preference for the distribution of monetary incentives; furthermore, this is the most impactful driver among the six tools (up to the Netherlands, where 48% of the decision is based on how incentives are framed).</p> <p>Non-monetary incentives support motivation and the sharing of values. Our test shows that women prefer this type of incentive, while elderly and citizens with low levels of education tend to prefer a non-monetary incentive as the second-best option, relative to monetary incentives.</p>
Strengths and weaknesses	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Comprehension and fast engagement. Monetary incentives are very simple and immediate to understand.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Clear communication. The rationale related to the use of monetary incentives should be clear, as its vagueness could lead to misunderstandings that may undermine the involvement over time. They should not be presented (and participants should not interpret them) as alternative salaries, which make this participation a sort of "second job".</p>

	<p>They should not be linked to tasks completion as it leads to the risk of considering “citizens performance” as the central aspect of the CSH activities.</p>
<p>How to apply it</p>	<p>Monetary incentives foster the intrinsic motivation of citizens, and it is supposed to be a strong, engaging incentive but, at the same time, it would be preferable to avoid that all the tasks are linked to financial incentives.</p> <p>Non-monetary incentives stimulate the prosocial motivation of citizens.</p> <p>Linking some tasks to non-monetary incentives would help to further stimulate participation, motivating different categories of participants (e.g., those who are interested in certificates for their personal growth or those mainly moved by intrinsic motivation).</p>

6.3.5 Types of stakeholders

Participants	
Description of the incentivisation tool	<p>Single or multiple stakeholder exchanges may favour citizen engagement in CSH. When looking at the teams that are built to group together participants and better organise the workload of their tasks, their composition may vary: on one side academics, who are usually the team leaders who manage the overall project and the specific tasks; on the other one, all those stakeholders that voluntarily decide to participate.</p> <p>Nevertheless, it could be the case that citizens are expected to work in mixed groups of peers and academics, in a group composed only of other citizens or together with academics only. This may vary depending on the nature of the project and on the requirements of the tasks (e.g., decision about the objectives, data collection, data analysis).</p>
When to apply it	<p>Mixed groups of stakeholders may be engaged at all CSH phases.</p> <p>Overall, within the four countries under study, there is a higher preference for cooperating in groups composed of a mix of academics and citizens, with the Netherlands being the only exception.</p>
Strengths and weaknesses	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Diverse inputs. Mixed groups have the great advantage that they allow sharing different perspectives, enriching the project overall and in particular on the aspects covered by those teams. Groups composed of only citizens tend to put a stronger focus on their point of view and their needs, which usually are the focal point of CSHs. When the single participant is involved in a group composed of academic scientists, this can be a unique opportunity to enjoy and be part of a scientific team; this can work as a strong motivator toward task involvement and completion.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Orchestration is required. Mixed groups could be chaotic and a potential source of friction, given that they "force" academics and citizens to work together and accept compromises to cooperate for a common goal. These attritions, if relevant or continuous during the project, can lead to participants' dropouts or decreased involvement in terms of tasks completion. If only citizens are involved in developing a specific task, the main risk lies in the potential lack of technical knowledge to proceed as well as a lack of top-down governance that addresses what should be done and organises the different activities. If a participant is involved in a group of academics only, the risk is that they exploit their position to limit her contributions to very simple tasks or exclude her from the activities due to a general lack of trust toward "non-scientists".</p>

How to apply it	Although with different degrees of preference share, the big picture that emerges is a general willingness towards working with a mixed group of citizens and academics. Then, depending on the tasks, the single RPOs could consider the local preferences to identify processes managed by only citizens and/or by only academic scientists.
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6.3.6 Motivation

Public value/Private interest	
Description of the incentivisation tool	<p>Motivation refers to caring to make a contribution. Motivation may be prosocial if it embeds the desire to protect and promote the wellbeing of others and intrinsic if seeks personal interests. This dichotomy relates to the final aim of the CSH, and broadly relates to the "topic of interest". While CSHs usually focus on issues that are recognised as relevant by the entire local community, there exist initiatives that aim at facing more general problematics (public value) while others that provide concrete benefits, particularly for those who participate (private interest).</p>
When to apply it	<p>Studies show that motivation may be used as a driver to manipulate citizens' behaviour toward a public policy or a specific program.</p> <p>As a consequence, CSH may put in place communication initiatives aimed at stimulating prosocial attitudes of citizens toward achieving public value. Communication to stimulate prosocial behaviour shall be framed positively, using fluent communication (i.e. bullet points) and ideally beneficiary contacts. All these tools are correlated with a greater willingness of citizens to engage proactively.</p>
Strengths and weaknesses	<p>What can go right</p> <p>Public value. Projects that focus on public value-related issues can be a relevant stimulus for those intrinsically motivated participants, who participate to genuinely contribute to the community. Including aspects that are more focused on citizens' private interests could foster the participation of those citizens that otherwise would not have sufficient interest in participating.</p> <p>What can go wrong</p> <p>Self-interest challenges. Specifically for what concerns projects that focus on private interest-related issues, this might attract stakeholders who are more "volatile" and might leave the project as soon as the project evolution loses compatibility with their interests.</p>
How to apply it	<p>In light of the overall preferences, the CSHs could set up the topic(s) of their future projects focusing on those that generate public value. The Lithuanian case requires some further reflections by the local RPFO, although the preference toward private interest-related issues is not so marked at all.</p>

6.4 How to develop a stakeholder engagement plan

Looking at the literature retrieved in Chapter 2, at further contributions (not specifically focused on drivers and barriers behind stakeholders' participation) and at the evidence emerging from the findings, it is possible to summarise those aspects that are relevant to develop a stakeholder engagement plan.

One of the first points to be addressed relates to the definition of team roles and responsibilities to create an internal structure. To this aim, it could be useful to involve external subjects who are already familiar with CS initiatives and/or with administrative and organisational skills, like external consultants, facilitators or subject matter experts.

Once the internal structure has been established, an overall timeline has to be defined, for what concerns stakeholders' recruitment and involvement, start of the activities, intermediate deadlines and end of the project. When stakeholders are engaged, it is important to share with them such a workflow and ask for their feedback, as the success of the CSH depends on the concrete feasibility of the tasks on the agreed timeline. Providing a too tight set of deadlines might increase participants' stress towards the completion of the tasks and result in a progressive dropout rate throughout the project.

Another internal organisational aspect to be defined relates to the definition of the project and its aim in function of the available resources and costs. This aspect affects participants' engagement, as resources constraints may affect the recruitment of facilitators, the development of material for continuous training, the possibility to reward participants, have a physical venue to meet, organise physical meetings and so on.

Once defined the internal organisation in light of economic and physical constraints, CSHs are ready to recruit participants. Depending on whether the issues to be addressed have already been defined or are going to be decided with the stakeholders, the recruitment process could be open to any volunteer or targeted to particular categories (e.g., those who already participated in previous CSHs, minorities or those stakeholders that are going to be the most affected by the CS activities).

After the recruitment process, participants need to be provided with adequate background material and information related to the issue that the CSH is going to address (if already defined), such that everyone has a common base of knowledge. The way such information is presented is particularly central, as a low degree of understanding in the initial phases implies few tasks completed and high dropout rates since the beginning of the project due to participants' inability to provide their contribution. As mentioned in the Chapter that presented the theoretical background, language should be plain, inclusive and accessible to all the audience.

With the start of the project and the activities, an element to consider is the potential involvement of expert facilitators. Their presence depends on the availability of adequate resources and on the perceived usefulness expressed by the participants (as seen in the survey). If there exist resources and consensus on their presence, they can play a relevant role: in fact, they provide guidance during the entire project, help the CSH in organising events and administrative tasks but also (and in particular) stakeholders in performing their tasks, in light of their previous experience.

During the project, in parallel with the intermediate tasks and deadlines mentioned above, it is important to plan adequate and detailed reporting activities for each of these objectives. This will help from different perspectives, each of them with a positive impact in terms of continuous citizens' engagement in the project to:

- Maintain and establish realistic deadlines for the prosecution of the project;
- Provide participants continuous feedback;
- Learn lessons for the future, both for the ongoing project and for future ones.

The more "administrative" information (e.g., number of events organised, participants, related costs) will be useful for the project managers to better tailor future events and for accountability purposes.

6.4.1 *Addressing potential barriers*

During the establishment process of a CSH and the implementation of the project, factors exist that may negatively affect stakeholders' participation and continuous engagement across time, as already presented in the theoretical background. Taking as reference the evidence that emerged from the survey, below we present some further potential barriers related to the implementation of the six tested tools. This process allows us to get further insights specific to the four local contexts, in addition to the general suggestions retrieved from the literature.

In terms of involvement mode, the suggestion to adopt a mixed approach (both online and in-person activities) derives from the risk of unintentionally excluding some categories of stakeholders that might be relevant to the project. This typically relates to those with limited mobility (from a physical or economic perspective) and, on the other side, to those with limited digital knowledge and instruments.

The presence of expert facilitators could be very useful for administrative and more practical purposes; nevertheless, how they present themselves could be a barrier in the long term, in particular if they implement a too paternalistic approach towards participants, which can result in general disappointment, discouragement and eventually dropouts from the project.

In terms of continuous training, we already mentioned the risk of becoming a too burdening task for participants, in particular when such activities are too many, too frequent, too difficult to understand or if participation is de facto compulsory to keep contributing to the project. This is relevant as lack of time has been frequently mentioned in other CSHs as one of the main barriers.

Monetary incentives have been shown to be the most impactful tool to attract participants. Nevertheless, it is important to not present them as alternative salaries, otherwise voluntary participation would become a sort of "second job" and stakeholders' "performance" would become the central aspect of the project. If this is the case, there is a concrete risk of losing throughout the project those participants that are moved by their intrinsic motivation and that are not particularly interested in receiving monetary rewards.

Looking at how team works could be established, an equilibrium has to be found in order to avoid dropouts depending on the composition of the teams. When the teams are composed of a mix of academics and other participants, the absence of elasticity in finding compromises in the overall approach and workload can discourage participants. In the case of involvement of only citizens, the main risk lies in the potential lack of technical knowledge to proceed, as well as a lack of top-down governance that addresses what should be done and organises the different activities. Finally, in case of involvement with academics only, the risk is that they could exploit their position to exclude participants from important activities due to a general lack of trust towards "non-scientists". If these risks are underestimated, participation could progressively decrease.

Finally, in terms of themes covered by the project, a focus on private interest-related issues might attract stakeholders who are more “volatile” and might leave as soon as the project evolution loses compatibility with their interests.

7. Implications and future work for the INCENTIVE project

Citizen science clearly has the potential to propel the design, implementation and uptake of solutions for the societal challenges that the EU has identified as a priority through the Horizon Europe Programme (2021-2027): (i) Health, demographic change and wellbeing; (ii) Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, water research, and bioeconomy; (iii) Secure clean and efficient energy; (iv) Smart, green and integrated transport; (v) Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw material; (vi) Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; (vii) Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens). The institutionalisation of citizen science in research performing as well as research funding organisations, such as the RPFOS of INCENTIVE, is a catalyst for this necessary change, as these types of organisations generally have a broad outlook and impact on their regional (and national) surroundings. To facilitate this transition, we are hereunder starting the discussion on policy recommendations for RPFOS, both those participating in INCENTIVE as well as those outside of it.

Considering the preference for participation by means of online tools, RPFOS should propel the digitalisation of participation means, and ensure a just and equitable access of all population groups (potential citizen scientists) to those means. This can be done both through research on digitalisation as well as the proper use of digital participation tools on the side of the RPFOS. The tools should be openly available, easy to understand, access, easy to use, and always supplemented by analogue participation options for those that cannot access them. Special attention should be made that awareness about the availability of those tools is not enhanced only in the academic setting, but throughout society, too.

Regarding the preference (or not) for the presence or absence of an expert facilitator, we suggest that each RPFOS should consider acquiring trained personnel to facilitate the implementation of citizen science, co-creation and design thinking methodologies in projects run by the RPFOS. These well-trained personnel will be tasked to support any kind of co-creation activity regardless of discipline, working alongside academic experts, researchers and students operating in different settings and within different disciplines. Even in the cases that they are not required to have an active presence (see the case of Lithuania), they will be able to provide the background knowledge, tools and methodologies to support the design and implementation of proper citizen science experiments. One of the foremost goals of INCENTIVE is to actually plant this knowledge and capacity to set up and run citizen science projects independently, so we envision that the project will have a major effect on this aspect on our RPFOS and beyond.

It goes without saying that all RPFOS should aspire to promote citizen science should have in place the appropriate training programs and mechanisms for setting up and running citizen science projects. It is far from necessary to set up whole new curricula and programmes, as citizen science resources have already been inventoried, practised on publicly open and available resources, such as ECSA's (INCENTIVE partner) EU-Citizen.Science platform (<https://eu-citizen.science/>), which recently acquired new funding through Horizon Europe to continue to be alive and enhanced over the upcoming years. It is needed, however, on the side of RPFOS, to sit down and contemplate which resources serve best their strategic priorities and fit best within their already established procedures and modes of doing science, and then make aware and train prospective citizen scientists on those tools and methods. INCENTIVE, again, presents a major opportunity for the RPFOS to access both these resources as well as know-how from ECSA and peers in order to make full use of them.

The provision of motivation to participate in citizen science is probably an issue that should be debated within and amongst RPFs. Although our findings suggest a very stark preference for the availability of monetary incentives for participation, there is a broader way of thinking about citizen science that is based on the notion that citizens should participate in those kinds of projects out of genuine interest, rather than the offering of monetary (or non-monetary) incentives. Arguably, this kind of engagement is expected to yield richer results and sustained interest over time. Thence our suggestion is that in the case that RPFs make a policy decision to establish mechanisms of financial compensation for participation in citizen science, then this should be a well-thought-out and justified decision, which should be supported by a steady income source for the RPFs so that the longevity of the mechanism is ensured.

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9. Appendix

Page 1 (Informed consent)

Continuing with this survey, I confirm that I read and understood the information contained in the "Informed consent" document. I am aware of the fact that my data will be processed anonymously in full compliance with the EU GDPR, and I give my consent to use the data in the manners described in the aforementioned document. I also declare that I know my rights as well as how to exercise them.

- I agree to participate to the questionnaire
- I do not agree (this option will remove you from the survey)

Page 2 (Socio-demographic characteristics)

1. Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other: _____
- I prefer not to answer

2. Age (at 1/1/2022):

- <18
- 18-19
- 20-24
- 25-29
- 30-34
- 35-39
- 40-44
- 45-49
- 50-54
- 55-59
- 60-64
- 65+

3. Current education level:

- Less than a high school diploma
- High school diploma (or equivalent)
- Bachelor's Degree (or equivalent)
- Master's Degree (or equivalent)
- Further post-Master studies (e.g. PhD)
- Other: _____

4. Main educational background:

- Arts and literature
- Natural sciences
- Health sciences
- Engineering and construction
- Architecture and urban planning
- Economics and finance
- Social sciences
- Other: _____

5. Current status (you can pick more than one option):

- Student
- Worker
- Entrepreneur
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other: _____

Page 3 (CS knowledge)

6. Do you know the meaning of the term “Citizen Science”?

- Yes
- No

Page 4 (CS definition)

The term “Citizen Science” refers to a scientific approach aimed at involving in scientific research also amateur/non-professional scientists (“citizens”), in cooperation with scientists and academics. This kind of engagement can take many forms and at different stages, from the definition of a research question (usually connected –but not limited– to local public policy issues) to the data collection process and the data analysis and discussion.

In other words, Citizen Science can be described as the systematic engagement of citizens in academic research.

Page 5 (Attention check)

7. Which of the following describes the concept of Citizen Science?

- Analysis of the behaviour of “individuals as citizens”.
- Approach used by scientists who use a friendly language to spread science (i.e., accessible to all citizens).
- Approach that considers the involvement of citizens in scientific research.
- Study of the impact of local policies on citizens.

Page 5 (Conjoint section – introduction)

Imagine to be involved in a Citizen Science project that focuses on a topic that you particularly care about (e.g., find innovative ways to reduce pollution, take care of fragile portions of the population, meet new people with common interests and hobbies).

In each of the next two screens you will see two alternative scenarios. Imagine two Citizen Science projects, that focus on the same topic and are completely identical, except for the characteristics listed in the scenarios. You are kindly asked to carefully read them and then choose in which project you would be more likely to participate.

Page 6 (Conjoint section)

Tool	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
<i>Mode of involvement</i>	Your involvement will be online, through a digital platform	Your involvement will be in person, through workshops	Your involvement will be in person, in the field
<i>Expert facilitator</i>	Your contribution will be guided by an expert facilitator who will promote commitment and collaboration	Your contribution will not be guided by an expert facilitator who will promote commitment and collaboration	
<i>Continuous training</i>	Throughout the project you will keep receiving continuous training and other tools to learn from the experience	Throughout the project you will not receive continuous training and other tools to learn from the experience	
<i>Incentive</i>	You will receive a small economic reward for your contribution	You will receive a small non-economic reward for your contribution	You will not receive any reward for your contribution
<i>Participants</i>	Your involvement will be with a mixed group of	Your involvement will be with only citizens	Your involvement will be with only

	citizens and academic researchers		academic researchers
<i>Public value/Private interest</i>	Your activities will contribute to generate value for the community	Your activities will contribute to satisfy individual needs	

8. Would you be willing to participate to a Citizen Science project that possesses the characteristics listed in the scenario you have chosen?
- Yes
 - No

Page 7 (Final questions)

9. Have you ever participated in Citizen Science projects?
- Yes
 - No
10. If you knew about a Citizen Science project on a topic you are interested in, would you be willing to participate?
- Absolutely not willing to participate
 - Probably not willing to participate
 - May be willing to participate
 - Probably willing to participate
 - Absolutely willing to participate
11. Could you please list the topics for which you would consider participating in a Citizen Science project (you can pick more than one option)?
- Health
 - Environmental sciences
 - Energy and sustainability
 - Public administration and policy
 - Information technologies
 - Circular economy
 - Communication sciences
 - Transport and mobility
 - Human media interaction
 - Educational sciences
 - Urban development and planning
 - Culture
 - Civil rights
 - Social welfare

Other: _____

Page 8 (Acknowledgements)

Thanks for having completed the questionnaire!

This survey has been developed in the framework of the Horizon 2020 INCENTIVE project, whose aim is to establish Hubs for Citizen Science development in four different countries (Greece, Lithuania, Spain and the Netherlands).

If you are curious and you want to know more about INCENTIVE (and Citizen Science), you can:

- [Visit the official website](#) of the project
- [Watch our promotional video](#)
- Follow us on [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [Linkedin](#) and [Youtube](#).

You can also subscribe to our newsletter, that will be sent to this e-mail: _____

INCENTIVE project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement (GA) No 101005330.

Table A1: CS-related questions per country

CS aspects		Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Previous knowledge of CS	Yes	58.8%	45.8%	47.7%	53.8%
	No	41.2%	54.2%	52.3%	46.2%
Previous participation on CS projects	Yes	12.3%	9.3%	17%	13%
	No	87.7%	90.7%	83%	87%
Probability to participate to "interesting" CS projects	Absolutely not	1.6%	10.2%	7.3%	4.1%
	Probably not	6.6%	14.4%	11%	6%
	Maybe	39.3%	42.4%	42.7%	29.8%
	Probably	38.9%	22.9%	30%	42.1%
	Absolutely	16.7%	10.2%	9%	18%
	Health	11.3%	12.6%	17.1%	11.6%
	Environmental sciences	7.5%	5.4%	5.7%	8.6%
Topics of interest of a hypothetical CS project	Energy and sustainability	8.1%	10.2%	9.2%	9.8%
	Public administration and policy	6%	6%	5.5%	4.3%
	Information technologies	7.5%	8.7%	5%	6.1%
	Circular economy	6.3%	3%	3.4%	5.1%
	Communication sciences	5.6%	7.8%	5.1%	4.8%
	Transportation and mobility	4%	6.9%	6.8%	7.6%
	Human media interaction	6.6%	6.3%	3.4%	5.2%
	Educational sciences	8.6%	4.5%	7.1%	7.9%
	Urban development and planning	3.2%	3.9%	5.5%	4.6%
	Culture	8.2%	6.9%	7.8%	7.8%
	Civil rights	10.9%	7.5%	8.5%	6.1%
	Social welfare	6%	9%	9%	10.3%
	Other	0.3%	1.5%	1%	0.4%
N		318	118	300	316

Table A2: Relevance of the six tools per country

Tools	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Mode of involvement	27%	29%	8.1%	18%
Expert facilitator	2.2%	5.2%	7.6%	14.3%
Continuous training	5.1%	11.2%	11.6%	12.3%
Incentive	39.2%	42.1%	48.2%	29.8%
Participants	22.2%	8.5%	16.3%	15.7%
Public value/Private interest	4.3%	3.8%	8.2%	9.9%
N	318	118	300	316

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

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